

2.5 cm of soil was removed and dried either in a hot air oven at 60°C for 24 hours or in sunlight for 2 to 3 days, This soil was used as inoculant. Normally, zygotes sprout into small seedlings 10 to 15 days after inoculation and mature

sporophytes develop within 20-25 days. The oven-dried zygotes germinated within 10-12 days; sun-dried zygotes germinated in 18-20 days.

The laboratory method allows researchers to raise azolla fronds from dried

materials and to transport azolla seed inoculum (dried zygotes), without damaging seed viability. This technique may also solve storage problems, sowing limitations imposed by summer, and help in azolla crossbreeding. □

Effect of summer plowing with different implements on wetland rice yields

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The effect of summer plowing with different implements on wetland rice yield and weed dry matter accumulation was studied during 1980 and 1981. Treatments were no tillage (control), plowing with country plow, tractor-drawn 11-tined cultivator, and tractor-drawn disc plow. Land was tilled in April and rice was transplanted in early July after puddling with a 10-hp power tiller. Soil was a sandy clay loam.

Plots tilled by disc plow had lowest weed population and yielded highest (see table). Weed dry matter accumulation was lowest after disc plowing,

Effect of summer plowing with different implements on rice gain yield and weed dry matter accumulation.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)			Weed dry matter accumulation (t/ha)		
	1980	1981	Mean	1980	1981	Mean
Control	2.4	2.0	2.2	2.1	2.7	2.4
Country plow	2.8	2.1	2.4	1.7	2.0	1.8
Cultivator	3.1	2.2	2.6	1.5	1.6	1.5
Disc plow	3.8	2.6	3.2	0.9	1.2	1.1
Mean	3.0	2.2	2.6	1.5	1.9	1.7
CD at 5%	0.1	0.2		0.1	0.04	

amounting to 0.9 t/ha in 1980 and 1.2 t/ha in 1981, followed by values for the cultivator and country plow.

Weed flora consisted mostly of *Cyperus rotundus* L., *Echinochloa crus-galli* (L.) Beauv., *Monochoria hastata* (L.) Solms, *Paspalum scrobiculatum* L., *Panicum* spp., *Hygrophila spinosa* T. Anders., *Oxalis* spp., *Emilia sonchifolia*

(L.) DC. ex Wight, *Setaria glauca* (L.) Beauv., *Cynodon dactylon* (L.) Pers., *Sporobolus diander* (Retz.) Beauv., *Chrysopogon* spp., *Caesulia axillaris* Roxb., *Saponaria vaccaria* L., *Spergula arvensis* L., *Jussiaea suffruticosa* L., *Polygonum plebeium* R. Br., and *Ageratum conyzoides* L., in decreasing order of population. □

Response of irrigated dry seeded rice to nitrogen level, interrow spacing, and seeding rate in a semiarid environment

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Semiarid soils are inherently nitrogen deficient, which limits rice yields. Although nitrogen fertilizers are expensive and unavailable in adequate quantities in many developing countries, relatively high rice yields can be obtained by optimizing spacing of rice plants in the field. We studied the interrelationship of nitrogen level, plant population and distribution pattern, and rice yield.

Three field experiments were conducted at the Gezira Research Station (13°30' – 15°5'N and 32°30' – 33°30' E) during 1977-79. Climate is semiarid and most rains (350-400 mm) fall during July and August. Soils are dark cracking Vertisols with 40-65% clay content.

Effect of nitrogen level, interrow spacing, and seeding rates on grain yield and some major yield components of irrigated dry seeded rice IR2053-206-1-36 in a semiarid environment in Sudan Gezira (av of 3 seasons 1977-79).

	Yield (t/ha)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Grains (no./panicle)	1000-grain weight (g)
<i>N (kg/ha)</i>				
60	4.2	343.2	70.8	23.17
120	4.8	386.6	78.3	23.64
180	6.4	411.1	80.1	23.91
<i>Interrow spacing (cm)</i>				
15	5.3	464.9	75.1	23.56
20	5.6	367.0	76.8	23.56
25	5.5	310.1	77.4	23.60
<i>Seeding rate (kg/ha)</i>				
50	5.5	358.7	82.2	23.48
100	4.4	382.8	76.5	23.64
150	5.5	400.5	70.5	23.60
S. E.	0.024	5.43	1.42	0.096

Treatments were 60, 120, and 180 kg N/ha as urea; 15, 20, and 25 cm interrow spacings; and 50, 100, and 150 kg seeds/ha. Treatments were grown in a randomized complete block design with

four replications. Land was prepared dry by plowing, disc harrowing, and leveling, then was divided by heavy ridges into 3.8 × 8.0 m plots. Immediately before seeding, 6.2 kg P/ha as superphosphate